

MECHANISMS OF FRACTURE IN DISCONTINUOUS METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The fracture behaviour and plane strain fracture toughness of three 8090 based metal matrix composites containing 20wt% SiC particles nominally 3, 13 and 23 μm in diameter has been evaluated. By measuring the change in elastic modulus with applied plastic strain stable void growth associated with SiC particle fracture has been identified. Further, it has been shown that the effect of SiC particle size on the fracture behaviour of these composite materials is consistent with that predicted by void growth models.

Keywords: fracture, modulus, strength.

1. INTRODUCTION

As would be expected wrought aluminium alloys are, in general, embrittled by the addition of a stiff ceramic reinforcement phase¹. The fracture behaviour of MMCs is complex but it is generally reported that the brittle fracture or decohesion of reinforcement precedes the ductile failure of the matrix²⁻⁴. A number of studies have concluded that damage in the composite is highly localised, only visible very close to the fracture surface and this indicates that strain localisation occurs early in the fracture process^{2,5}. Generally fractographic examination reveals three features: i) fractured SiC, ii) voids associated with failure of the matrix adjacent to the Al / SiC interface and iii) fine dimples, of the order of 1 μm in diameter, associated with void nucleation at precipitates, dispersoids, inclusions and grain boundaries.

The elastic modulus of discontinuously reinforced MMCs is a function of the volume fraction and aspect ratio of the reinforcement and the ability to transfer load to the reinforcement across the interface. Previous work has linked the degradation of elastic modulus with increasing plastic strain to damage to the reinforcement, in the form of particle cracking or interfacial decohesion⁶. In this study the elastic modulus of both reinforced and unreinforced materials was measured as a function of both tensile and compressive plastic strain in an attempt to identify void nucleation events.

From the literature it is evident that void nucleation ahead of a sharp crack tip is likely to be associated with the reinforcement phase, and therefore an effect of SiC particle size, for a homogenous distribution and at a constant reinforcement volume fraction, on fracture toughness may be expected. However, previous work on powder formed MMCs has shown that reducing the SiC particle size relative to the alloy powder particle size increases the tendency for clustering of the reinforcement and this has been shown to promote fracture initiation, making the identification of

other particle size related trends problematic⁷. In this study the plane strain fracture toughness of an 8090 matrix reinforced with 20wt% SiC nominally 3, 13 and 23 μm in diameter is related to the tensile properties, which are varied for a given reinforcement distribution by artificially ageing the matrix. The composites contain a homogenous distribution of reinforcement, and therefore the transition from fine to coarse reinforcement, with an increasing tendency for particle fracture, provides an opportunity to compare the effect of the particle failure mechanism on K_{IC} .

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The material for the study consisted of an 8090 matrix (Al-2.2Li-1.2Cu-0.7Mg-0.1Zr,wt%) reinforced with 20wt% of nominally 3, 13 and 23 μm particulate SiC and unreinforced 8090. The composite and unreinforced control alloy were produced by BP Metal Composites Ltd., using a powder metallurgy route involving hot isostatic pressing, hot forging and finally hot rolling to a plate thickness of 15 mm. In an attempt to minimise particle fracture during processing the powder and SiC were only lightly blended. The 8090 powder had a mean diameter of 30 μm . Examination of the composite microstructures revealed a relatively homogenous particle distribution (Figure 1) with little evidence of cracked particles in the final microstructures.

Figure 1. Distribution of SiC in the L-S plane in the (a) 3 μm , (b) 13 μm and (c) 23 μm composites.

The plate material was solution treated at 530°C for 2 hrs followed by cold water quenching. To avoid any effect of lithium loss during mechanical processing and heat treatment the surfaces of the plate were machined off and single edge notch bend specimens of dimensions 12.5x12.5x100 mm were taken from the T-S orientation. These specimens were then aged at 170°C and the ageing response was characterised in terms of 0.2% proof stress determined from Hounsfield specimens machined with the tensile axis parallel to T.

As a result of the reported lack of linearity in the initial loading curve it has been suggested that the elastic modulus of an MMC should be measured either after low amplitude fatigue cycling or from the unloading curve after minimal bulk plastic flow⁸. In this work the elastic modulus, at a given plastic strain, was measured subsequent to fatigue cycling. Ten low stress amplitude cycles in the range -70 MPa to +70 MPa were applied, and the elastic modulus was measured by fitting a straight line to the data, in the range -50 MPa to +50 MPa, generated on subsequent loading. The specimens were fatigue cycled to stabilise the dislocation structure such that the data in the lower stress range, generated on subsequent loading should be virtually unaffected by dislocation movement. The plastic strain was measured by fitting a line, the slope of which was equivalent to the fatigue modulus, calculated as above, to the unloading curve. Using this approach the error in elastic modulus for a given test was found to be approximately ± 0.5 GPa

Fracture toughness testing was performed according to BS 5447:1977 and all the data quoted are valid as stipulated apart from the 13 and 23 μm composites aged for 5 hrs at 170°C where the (W-a) dimension is too small. However the load / clip gauge displacement curves showed little evidence of plasticity and the fracture surfaces were macroscopically flat, without any shear lip development, so these data are considered valid.

Extensive fractographic studies were carried out in a CAMSCAN S2 SEM, at 20kV, in order to identify the failure mechanisms operating. The microstructure of each composite was characterised using a Phillips 400T TEM. For investigation of the matrix microstructure foils were prepared by jet polishing in a 25% nitric acid in ethanol solution at -20°C and for characterisation of the Al / SiC interface specimens were polished to 10 μm and ion beam thinned.

3. RESULTS

As illustrated in Figure 1 the distribution of SiC in each of the composites is homogenous and the average particle size subsequent to processing increases from 2.6 μm in the 3 μm composite to 4.8 μm in the 13 μm composite to 8.0 μm in the 23 μm composite⁹. The TEM study showed an unrecrystallised microstructure with a 1-2 μm sub-grain size for all the composites and in the unreinforced material the sub-grain size ranged from 2-4 μm . Each material contains approximately 0.5 wt% of Al₂O₃ and MgO as a result of the oxidation of the powder during processing. The composite matrix and the unreinforced control alloy are strengthened by the homogenous precipitation of δ' which forms from the quench. At longer ageing times there is evidence of heterogeneous and homogenous precipitation of S phase. Peak strength in the composites is achieved after 66 hrs at 170 °C (PA). For the purposes of this work an underaged temper (UA) was also employed, 5 hrs at 170 °C. Examination of the Al / SiC interface revealed that it was well bonded. A δ' precipitate free zone forms at the interface on ageing the width of which was measured to be approximately 100 nm after ageing for 66 hrs at 170 °C.

Figure 2. The elastic modulus as a function of plastic strain in the UA unreinforced 8090 and in the 23 μm composite.

From Figure 2 it is apparent that in the unreinforced material in the UA condition the elastic modulus does not vary with increasing plastic strain when testing in tension or in compression. The full range of data gathered are not shown, however one specimen was tested in tension up to failure, at a strain of 0.073, and the stiffness remained constant up to the final re-load. In the 23 μm composite tested in the UA condition, again in compression, the elastic modulus does not vary with plastic strain whereas in tension the elastic modulus fell from 106.4 GPa at zero plastic strain to 102.1 GPa at a plastic strain of 0.011. The difficulty in testing the composite materials was that, because of the limited strain to failure, few data points could be generated if a significant amount of plastic strain was applied between each measurement. Due to limited material availability the degradation in elastic modulus, with plastic strain, in the 3 μm and 13 μm materials could not be measured.

The 0.2% proof stress and plane strain fracture toughness data for each of the composites in the UA and PA condition are shown in table 1. For each composite fracture toughness decreases as the 0.2% proof stress increases and toughness increases with increasing particle size.

Material	5 hrs at 170°C (UA)		66 hrs at 170°C (PA)	
	PS (MPa)	K_{IC} (MPa $\sqrt{\text{m}}$)	PS (MPa)	K_{IC} (MPa $\sqrt{\text{m}}$)
3 μm	437	16.0	446	12.4
13 μm	352	19.2	410	14.5
23 μm	362	22.2	410	17.3

Table 1. Summary of the plane strain fracture toughness and 0.2% proof stress (PS) data.

Figure 3 shows typical fracture surfaces of the UA 3 μm and 23 μm composites. For both composites there is evidence of plasticity associated with particle fracture and matrix failure.

Figure 3. Comparison of the fracture surfaces, from pre-cracked specimens, in the UA (a) 3 μm and (b) 23 μm composites.

4. DISCUSSION

The mean field model has been shown to predict accurately the modulus of composites reinforced with particles¹⁰. The aspect ratio of the reinforcement in the 23 μm composite was measured and found to be approximately 1.5. Using the measured value of matrix stiffness of 78 GPa and assuming the stiffness of the SiC = 480 GPa, analysis predicts the elastic modulus to be 102.8

GPa¹¹ compared with a measured value of 106.4 GPa. The increase in elastic modulus, due to the addition of reinforcement, predicted from the mean field model is approximately a linear function of the volume fraction, f , of SiC up to 17vol%. Therefore using the predicted value of elastic modulus of 102.8 GPa at 17vol% the composite stiffness as a function of volume fraction of reinforcement is given by

$$E_{\text{comp}} = (78 + 146f) \text{ GPa} \quad (1)$$

If the reduction in stiffness measured up to the failure of the 23 μm composite, of 4.3 GPa, is subtracted from the modulus predicted from Equation 1 the new stiffness corresponds to $f=0.14$ of reinforcement. In the control alloy there was no loss of stiffness with increasing tensile plastic strain and in the UA 23 μm composite there was no loss of stiffness with compressive plastic strain. Figure 4 shows the fracture surface of a specimen tested in uniaxial tension and there is clearly a significant level of SiC particle fracture. There was no evidence of decohesion of the Al / SiC interface which from the TEM study was found to be well bonded.

Figure 4. Tensile fracture surface of the UA 23 μm composite.

If it is assumed the loss of stiffness, with applied plastic strain up to failure, in the 23 μm composite system is attributed to particle fracture this corresponds to the fracture of $f=0.03$ or ~18% of the reinforcement. This value could be interpreted as being a lower bound since the mechanism of load transfer would be expected to operate, albeit much less effectively, even when the reinforcement has fractured. From Figure 4 it is obvious that the extent of fracture of the SiC reinforcement is significantly greater than 3% of the fracture surface. The evidence suggests that particles fracture occurs at a strain considerably less than the failure strain and that there must be stable void growth associated with these fractured particles prior to final failure. However, it is also apparent that SiC also fractures at failure and there would be no stable void growth associated with this.

In the plastic zone ahead of a sharp crack tip the stress across the Al / SiC interface is significantly greater than in the uniaxial tension test¹³ such that in the 23 μm composite it would be reasonable to assume that the critical stress for particle fracture is achieved at the majority of SiC within the plastic zone. Comparing the effect of particle size on fracture toughness in the present composites is complicated by the fact that the 0.2% proof stress in a given ageing condition is a function of the nominal SiC size. If fracture initiation toughness is characterised in terms of crack tip opening displacement, δ_{IC} , then the effect of 0.2% proof stress on K_{IC} , for a given ageing condition can be accounted for, since in plane strain:

$$\delta_{IC} = \frac{K_{IC}^2}{2E\sigma_{ys}} \quad (2)$$

The centre-to-centre SiC spacing for each of the composites can be calculated from the average SiC diameters using Equation 3

$$\lambda = \left[\frac{4\pi}{3f} \right]^{1/3} r \quad (3)$$

δ_{IC} has been calculated for each of the composites in the UA and PA conditions using Equation 2 and is plotted against λ in Figure 5. Clearly for a given ageing condition δ_{IC} is proportional to λ , and in a given composite δ_{IC} decreases as the ageing time is increased.

Figure 5. δ_{IC} plotted against the SiC interparticle spacing.

The relationship $\delta_{IC} = \lambda$ was proposed by Hahn and Rosenfield¹², working on the fracture of unreinforced aluminium alloys, on the basis of the analysis of Rice and Johnson¹³ which showed that the extent of the region of large plastic deformation ahead of a crack tip is approximately equal to the crack tip opening displacement. Hahn and Rosenfield postulated that crack extension proceeds when the extent of the heavily deformed region ahead of the crack tip is comparable to the width of the unbroken ligaments separating cracked particles. This approach assumes that voids nucleate at second phase particles instantaneously and grow to coalescence. From Figure 3 there is evidence of void growth associated with SiC particle fracture in both the 3 μm and 23 μm composites but the coalescence of primary voids is preceded by the ductile fracture of the matrix. This explains why, in both tempers, δ_{IC} is less than λ . Also at fracture initiation δ_{IC} decreases with increasing 0.2% proof stress. Previous work on similar composite materials has also shown that the fracture initiation toughness decreases with increasing 0.2% proof stress and this was attributed to stress-controlled void nucleation in the matrix occurring at lower applied strains².

It is generally observed that the propensity for SiC fracture decreases as particle size increases. In the present study it was found that this was difficult to confirm from fractography since the finer reinforcement is less visible on the fracture surface. It is likely that void initiation will occur at or local to the interface of fine SiC, due to load transfer to the reinforcement, and that coarser SiC which is inherently weaker may fracture before or during such a process. The implications of Figure 5 are that fracture initiation in the present materials is determined by primary void growth and matrix failure rather than the nucleation of voids at SiC. Therefore in terms of determining the initiation toughness the effect of SiC size on the mechanism of primary void nucleation does not appear to be critical.

5. CONCLUSIONS

For each of the composites it has been shown that ageing to peak 0.2% proof stress results in a decrease in plane strain fracture toughness. Primary void initiation is associated with the SiC and there is evidence of void growth prior to failure, which occurs by the ductile rupture of the ligaments separating the primary voids. To account for the variation in 0.2% proof stress between composites given the same ageing treatment fracture initiation toughness was characterised in terms of the crack tip opening displacement, δ_{IC} . As the SiC interparticle spacing was increased it was shown that δ_{IC} increased also as predicted by contemporary void growth models.

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METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES: INTERFACE

